

CARE 2026: Comprehensive Analysis of REal-world medical images - heart and liver: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

CARE 2026: Comprehensive Analysis of REal-world medical images - heart and liver

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

CARE 2026

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Real-world medical imaging data pose distinct challenges, including variability in imaging modalities, distribution shifts due to diverse data acquisition protocols across centers, and irregular regions of interest (ROIs) such as lesions and scars. Recently, deep learning has made huge progress in medical image analysis. Specifically, the rise of foundation models like the Segment Anything Model (SAM) has revolutionized healthcare AI by demonstrating remarkable performance across a range of tasks.

However, their effectiveness in real-world medical imaging scenarios faces three main challenges. First, organs vary greatly in size, shape, texture, and position, making models difficult to generalize across multiple tasks that target different organs. In addition, organs share intrinsic anatomical and functional consistency, overlooking these cross-organ correlations poses a significant challenge to model analysis. Second, a patient might undergo several types of imaging tests, like CT scans and MRIs, resulting in multi-modality medical images. And finally, in real-world scenarios, data often comes from multiple centers, regions, countries, and continents, which leads to the varying distributions of datasets.

We sum up these real-world challenges as multi-organ and multi-continent. Such challenges are particularly evident in real-world data characterized by high variability and clinical complexity. For instance, in segmentation tasks involving myocardial pathology and lesions or scars, targets are often small, irregularly shaped, and structurally intricate. Addressing real-world challenges is essential for adapting foundation models to clinical settings, thereby advancing medical image analysis and improving patient outcomes.

In this Challenge, we create a platform to tackle the real-world challenges in four scenarios. Specifically, we provide comprehensive datasets comprising over 2000 cases from 18 centers across 3 continents, thus provide

multi-continental representation. Besides, we focus on structure and pathology segmentation in two key organs: the heart and the liver, from CT and MRI datasets. The challenge will feature four tasks, CARE-Left Atrium, CARE-Liver, CARE-Myocardium, and CARE-Whole Heart. We encourage participants to not only address real-world challenges in a single task, but also to explore the potential of foundation models to capture the correlations between different continents, different modalities, and different organs. Addressing the complexities of real-world medical imaging analysis.

Two previous editions of CARE challenge were held in 2024 and 2025, respectively. In CARE 2024, we had 150 teams participating, accepted 23 papers (9 oral presentations), and conducted over 450 online evaluations. In CARE 2025, we extended the challenge with the inclusion of over 850 newly collected cases and improved the evaluation methodology. As a result, the number of teams that participated in CARE 2025 increased to 248, by around 65%. After a double-blind review process, CARE 2025 accepted 23 papers with an acceptance rate of 48%, and selected 8 of them as oral presentations. In total, 476 online evaluations had been conducted.

Based on CARE 2025, we extend the challenge with the following enhancements:

(1) Inclusion of 710 newly collected cases, comprising 300 CT scans for the return of CARE-Left Atrium, 190 MRI scans CARE-Liver, 200 cardiac MRIs for CARE-Myocardium and 20 CTA scans for CARE-Whole Heart.

(2) We propose the CARE-Left Atrium track, extending the Left Atrial and Scar Quantification & Segmentation (LAScarQS++) track in CARE 2024, and now consisting of 194 LGE MRIs and 300 CT scans from 4 centers across 3 continents. Compared with the previous events, this track proposes a new segmentation sub-task targeting left atrium, left atrial appendage and pulmonary veins.

(3) We extend the myocardial pathology segmentation (MyoPS) track in CARE 2025 and propose the CARE-Myocardium track. This track now has a collection of Cine, LGE and T2 CMR sequences for 500 patients scans from 9 centers, and on the basis of the original track, we add a new sub-task that focus on segmenting myocardial pathology regions on the Cine sequence.

[Challenges of real-world medical images]

Multi-organ: Real-world medical tasks on different organs often involve ROIs with irregular shapes and small sizes, such as lesions or scars. These irregularities challenge the ability of models to produce accurate and clinically meaningful segmentation results. Moreover, organs share intrinsic anatomical and functional consistency. Overlooking these cross-organ correlations poses a significant challenge to model analysis.

Multi-continent: Images from various countries, regions and continents differs in acquisition parameters, devices and patient status. These variations result in the extreme inhomogeneity of imaging data, which challenge the generalization capabilities of models.

[Objectives]

Foster Generalizability on Real-world Medical Images: Evaluate the generality of models across multiple tasks and imaging modalities from different centers cross different continents, enabling broader clinical applicability.

Develop Transfer Learning Approaches: Encourage participants to develop innovative transfer learning or finetuning techniques for adapting foundation models to diverse and complex real-world medical imaging scenarios.

Benchmark Performance: Provide a comprehensive benchmarking framework for assessing the performance of

algorithms on five tracks, fostering reproducibility in medical image analysis.

[Datasets]

The challenge will release four diverse datasets designed to address specific clinical requirements. These datasets target organs with significant deformation (e.g., heart and liver) and comprise over 2000 cases across 3 continents. Key features of the datasets include:

Multi-Continental Representation: Data acquired from centers in three continents ensures diversity in patient demographics and imaging protocols.

Multi-Modality: A variety of imaging modalities are encompassed, reflecting the heterogeneity of real-world clinical practice.

Intrinsic Misalignment: Challenges posed by respiratory motion and cardiac pulsation are embedded in the datasets, simulating real-world conditions.

Missing Data: Scenarios with missing modalities are included to reflect practical limitations in clinical imaging.

[Challenge Tracks]

The challenge will feature four tracks, each addressing a specific aspect of medical image analysis:

CARE-Left Atrium: The target of this track is to segment LA structures (targeting left Atrium, left atrial appendage and pulmonary veins) from CT scans, and achieve segmentation of the LA cavity and quantification of LA scars using LGE MRI scans. Key challenges include variability across multi-center data, complex LA shapes, thin atrial walls, surrounding enhanced regions, and intricate scar patterns in AF patients.

CARE-Liver: This track consists of two tasks, focusing on developing automated methods for liver segmentation and fibrosis staging using multi-phase, multi-center liver MRI scans. Major challenges include missing modalities, misalignments in multi-phase MRI data, limited ground truth annotations, and domain shifts in multi-center datasets.

CARE-Myocardium: This track solely focuses on myocardial pathology segmentation from multi-sequence cardiac magnetic resonance (MS-CMR) images in two scenarios: using Cine, LGE and T2 CMR sequences to segment Cine data, and segment bSSFP, LGE and T2 CMR sequences at once, to overcome challenges such as the inclusion of multi-center data, missing sequences for some centers, and misalignments in multi-sequence CMRs.

CARE-Whole Heart: The objective of this track is to achieve whole heart segmentation from MRI and CT scans. Methods are required to segment seven substructures, including left ventricular blood cavity (LV), right ventricular blood cavity (RV), left atrial blood cavity (LA), right atrial blood cavity (RA), myocardium of the left ventricle (Myo), ascending aorta (AO), and pulmonary artery (PA), from MRI and CT scans, with robustness against domain shifts from distinct modalities, different centers, and shape variability.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Real-world medical image analysis, Left atrium CT and MRI, Liver MRI fibrosis staging and segmentation, Whole heart segmentation, Myocardium pathology segmentation

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

This challenge aims to bridge the gap between AI technologies and their real-world impact in healthcare that involve complex and clinically significant challenges. Its novelty lies in the following:

Focus on Clinically Challenging Tasks: By prioritizing tasks like myocardial pathology (Myocardium), liver fibrosis staging (Liver), and lesion or scar quantification (Left Atrium), the challenge highlights issues that demand high precision and robustness.

Comprehensive and Diverse Dataset: Incorporating multi-continental, multi-modal, and clinically realistic datasets ensures a rich environment for testing model generalizability and adaptability.

Real-World Complexity: By embedding real-world challenges like multi-organ and multi-continent, the competition mirrors practical scenarios, promoting solutions that are directly translatable to clinical practice.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The challenge addresses four real-world medical imaging tasks with significant clinical relevance, each targeting different aspects of medical image analysis.

CARE-Left Atrium: This task targets the segmentation of the left atrium (LA) and quantification of LA scars from late gadolinium-enhanced (LGE) MRI and CT images. LA segmentation is crucial for automated LA analysis and contribute to improved diagnostic and therapeutic strategies for Atrial fibrillation (AF), the most prevalent arrhythmia encountered in clinical practice. Therefore, the envisioned impact of this task is to enable more precise diagnosis and personalized treatment planning for atrial fibrillation (AF) patients.

CARE-Liver: This task involves segmenting liver tissue and assessing fibrosis stages, which is crucial for understanding and managing liver diseases such as cirrhosis and liver malignancies, including hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma (ICC). The potential impact of this task is to improve the diagnosis and treatment planning for various types of chronic liver diseases, such as cirrhosis and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD).

CARE-Myocardium: This task focuses on segmenting myocardial lesions and scars, which are often small, irregularly shaped, and structurally complex. Accurate segmentation in this domain is critical for diagnosing conditions like myocardial infarction, fibrosis, and other heart diseases. Therefore, by addressing these challenges, accurate diagnosis, treatment planning and prognostic efficacy assessment of myocardial infarction (MI) can be improved.

CARE-Whole Heart: This task aims to achieve automatic whole heart segmentation from MRI and CT scans, which is essential for diagnosing cardiovascular diseases, planning surgical interventions, and conducting quantitative

analyses of heart morphology. The improvement of whole heart segmentation has the potential to detect subtle functional abnormalities of the heart to assist early diagnosis of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) patients, and support surgical guidance.

These tasks highlight the real-world challenges of medical image analysis, particularly in diverse clinical settings, and the need for adaptable, generalizable models capable of addressing Multi-organ, Multi-modality, and Multi-continent challenges in complex data with high variability, misalignments, and irregular ROIs.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

We plan to present a summary of the challenge, announce the results of all tracks. Moreover, we intend to organize a proceeding and select the oral papers among four tracks, with the authors of these papers invited to give oral presentations. We estimate that around 8 papers will be chosen.

Additionally, we will invite one or two keynote speakers to deliver talks related to the challenge.

Our previous edition CARE 2025 featured one keynote and 8 oral presentations, and it lasted half a day.

Therefore, we estimate that the challenge will also require a half-day slot.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

280.

In our first edition CARE 2024, we had 150 teams participating. Moreover, the number of teams that participated in CARE 2025 increased to 248.

Therefore, we expect the number of participating teams to reach at least 280.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

1. We consider to submit a proceeding.
2. We may consider to submit a benchmark paper.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS

proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

1 projector, 1 computer (or 1 laptop), 1 monitor, 2 loud speakers, 3 microphones

TASK 1: CARE-Left Atrium: Left Atrial Segmentation and Analysis

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most prevalent arrhythmia encountered in clinical practice, affecting approximately 1% of the population, with its incidence rising markedly with age. Precisely determining the location and extent of left atrial (LA) scars is essential for understanding the underlying mechanisms and progression of AF.

This task focuses on achieving (semi-)automatic segmentation of the LA cavity and quantification of LA scars using multi-center late gadolinium enhancement (LGE) MRI and CT scans. Key challenges include variability across multicenter data, complex LA shapes, thin atrial walls, surrounding enhanced regions, and intricate scar patterns in AF patients.

By addressing these challenges, this task aims to advance automated LA analysis and contribute to improved diagnostic and therapeutic strategies for AF. Ultimately, these improvements will enable more precise diagnosis and personalized treatment planning for atrial fibrillation (AF) patients.

CARE-Left Atrium has 2 sub-tasks: LA scar quantification from MRI (LASQ-MRI) and LA multi-structure segmentation from CT (LAMS-CT). Building on the data used in CARE 2024, we adopted the original two sub-tasks, i.e., LA scar quantification and LA cavity segmentation, merging them into the LASQ-MRI subtask. Moreover, we have added the new LAMS-CT sub-task. This sub-task targets segmenting Left Atrium (LA), left atrial appendage (LAA), and pulmonary veins (PVs), and consists of 300 newly collected CT scans from patients with AF from an additional center. These images were obtained with Siemens Force. The data were acquired at a resolution various from (0.30 x 0.30 x 0.5) to (0.80 x 0.80 x 0.5) mm. This expansion offers an enriched multi-continent resource for training and evaluating algorithms from multi-modality images, fostering the development of more robust and generalizable methods.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Atrial Fibrillation, Left Atrium, Segmentation, Scar Quantification, Generalizability

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Xiahai Zhuang, School of Data Science, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Liqin Huang, College of Physics and Information Engineering, Fuzhou University, Fuzhou, China.

Xingtao Lin, Department of College of Physics and Information Engineering Fuzhou University, Fuzhou, China.

Yazhou Lin, Department of Cardiology, Fuzhou University Affiliated Provincial Hospital, Fuzhou, China.

Xuwen Liao, Department of Cardiology, Fuzhou University Affiliated Provincial Hospital, Fuzhou, China.

Zhi Dou, Department of Cardiovascular Surgery, Fuzhou University Affiliated Provincial Hospital, Fuzhou, China.
 Huashan Huang, Department of Cardiology, Fuzhou University Affiliated Provincial Hospital, Fuzhou, China.
 Madina Mansurova, Department of Artificial Intelligence & Big Data, al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan.
 Lei Li, Department of Biomedical Engineering, National University of Singapore, Singapore.
 Jichao Zhao, Auckland Bioengineering Institute, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand.
 Zijie You, College of Physics and Information Engineering, Fuzhou University, Fuzhou, China.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Xiahai Zhuang: zxh@fudan.edu.cn

Liqin Huang: hlq@fzu.edu.cn

Xingtao Lin: 231110040@fzu.edu.cn

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes.

Yazhou Lin: Dataset curation and annotation.

Xuwen Liao: Dataset curation and annotation.

Zhi Dou: Dataset annotation.

Huashan Huang: Dataset curation.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

N/A

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly,

your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

No

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

https://www.zmic.org.cn/care_2026/

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples).

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants may also include publicly available data, including (open) pre-trained nets.

Such additional data needs to be publicly available before the date of the test results submission.

Private annotations of such data is prohibited.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May not participate

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge has one best paper and two runner-ups. In addition, each (sub)task has one best performance award.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

We will release the leaderboard to announce performance results of all methods publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Every member in the participating teams qualifies as author.

The participating teams may publish their own results separately, and are required to cite our challenge.

There is an embargo time.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

We established an online evaluation platform and plan to use Docker for the testing phase. During the training and validation phases, participants can register on our platform and directly upload their predictions on the validation set.

To ensure a fair comparison, we adopt Docker for the testing phase, requiring participants to submit their Docker models for testing. The memory limit is pre-defined to 20GB. If any problem occurs in testing, we will contact participants through email and report corresponding error reason.

Please see the challenge website (https://www.zmic.org.cn/care_2026/) for submission guidance. An example of a container will be provided on the challenge website, with the input/output information for each task displayed in that example.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Maximum number of model evaluations on the validation set: 10 in total after the submission platform opens.

Maximum number of final model evaluations on the test set: 1 in total.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration period: April 1st, 2026 - July 20th, 2026

Training data release: April 10st, 2026

Validation data release: May 1st, 2026

Test data release: June 20th, 2026

Test results submission: July 20th, 2026

Submission of abstract: July 30th, 2026

Submission of challenge paper: July 30th, 2026

Release date of final results: August 13th, 2026

Notification of challenge paper acceptance: August 13th, 2026

Challenge paper camera ready: August 27th, 2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

No ethics approval is needed.

The study had been approved by the institutional review board and the data had been anonymized.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The source code of evaluation won't be available. However, we will provide an online evaluation platform for long-term research purposes. We will ensure the online evaluation platform running smoothly, and prepare backup plans for emergencies. The metrics we adopted are commonly used in community and easy to reproduce the results. In addition, we will update a transparent specification for evaluation on the challenge website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants are encouraged to publish their code.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The sponsors are not decided yet.

Only organizers can have access to the test data labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD,Treatment planning,Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final

biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Atrial fibrillation patients who underwent cardiac LGE MRI or CT pre-or after-ablation.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is same as the target cohort.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

LGE MRI and CT.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional information.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

LA region shown in LGE MRI and CT.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

LA scar quantification from MRI: Scar regions in the LA wall and LA cavity region

LA multi-structure segmentation from CT: LA, left atrial appendage (LAA), and pulmonary veins (PVs).

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness,generalizability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Siemens Avanto 1.5T, Siemens Vario 3T, Philips Acheiva 1.5T, Siemens Force.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Images in this task were collected from 4 centers, namely 1.A/B/C/D.

Dataset 1.A: The clinical images were acquired with Siemens Avanto 1.5T or Vario 3T using free-breathing(FB)with navigator-gating. The spatial resolution of one 3D LGE-MRI scan was $1.25 \times 1.25 \times 2.5$ mm. The patients underwent an MR examination prior to ablation or was 3-6 months after ablation.

Dataset 1.B: Current clinical images were acquired with Philips Acheiva 1.5T using FB and navigator-gating with fat suppression. The spatial resolution of one 3D LGE-MRI scan was $1.3 \times 1.3 \times 4.0$ mm. The patients underwent an MR examination prior to ablation or was 3-6 months after ablation.

Dataset 1.C: The clinical images were also acquired with Philips Acheiva 1.5T using FB and navigator-gating with fat suppression. The spatial resolution of one 3D LGE-MRI scan was $1.4 \times 1.4 \times 1.4$ mm. The patients underwent an MR examination prior to ablation or was 1 month after ablation.

Dataset 1.D: The clinical CT images were acquired with Siemens Force. The data were acquired at a resolution various from $(0.30 \times 0.30 \times 0.5)$ to $(0.80 \times 0.80 \times 0.5)$ mm.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The data for this task was collected from 4 centers listed above across three continents.

In consideration of patient and institutional privacy and confidentiality, along with the study purpose of model generalizability, detailed information regarding the source of specific sub-datasets for each task will not be disclosed.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Experienced physicists specialized in cardiac MRI and CT.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to an MRI/CT image with golden standard LA structure and scar annotations.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

This task has 494 cases in total.

For LA scar quantification from MRI (LASQ-MRI):

For scar quantification,

Training set: 60 cases {Centers:1.A=60}

Validation set: 10 cases {Centers:1.A=10}

Testing set: 24 cases {Centers:1.A=24}

For cavity segmentation,

Training set: 130 cases {Centers:1.A=130}

Validation set: 20 cases {Centers:1.A=10, 1.C=10}

Testing set: 44 cases {Centers:1.A=14, 1.B=20, 1.C=10}

LA multi-structure segmentation from CT (LAMS-CT):

Training set: 130 cases {Centers:1.D=130}

Validation set: 20 cases {Centers:1.D=20}

Testing set: 150 cases {Centers:1.D=150}

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

For LA scar quantification from MRI (LASQ-MRI), all cases are annotated with LA cavity label. 94 cases are annotated with LA scar label.

For LA multi-structure segmentation from CT (LAMS-CT), Training set: 23%, Validation set: 100%, Test set: 33%.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

1. The task of this challenge is arduous, so sufficient training data is required to ensure reasonable performance. Therefore, the proportion of training and test is chosen for both subtasks.
2. The inclusion of both pre-ablation and post-ablation LGE MRI for LA segmentation, while solely requesting scar quantification on post-ablation LGE MRI, aligns with clinical needs of ablation efficacy assessment and technical considerations for segmentation accuracy.
3. For LA scar quantification from MRI (LASQ-MRI), the total number of cases is limited, because few patients underwent scanning of LGE MRI. More importantly, labeling the images manually is laborious and time-consuming.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

None.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Yes. In this task, we include 300 more CT scans from a new center, referred to as 1.D, to enrich the open-access dataset released in CARE 2024. Addition of new data enables to support a new subtask of segmenting Left Atrium (LA), left atrial appendage (LAA), and pulmonary veins (PVs). The proportion of new data is $300/494 = 60.72\%$.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Each data had been manually delineated by doctor or well-trained observers who were not aware of the methodology of this work.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For the segmentation label, the annotators were instructed to segment the ROIs slice-by-slice, using the brush tool in the ITK-SNAP.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each task was conducted by different radiologists specialized in this field. For each task, PhD students first independently finished the annotation for each case and the average annotation was then checked and amended by a senior radiologist.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The final gold standard segmentation was achieved by averaging several manual delineations using the shape-based average approach if necessary.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

None.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Inter- and intra-annotator variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

For LA scar quantification from MRI (LASQ-MRI):

LA cavity segmentation: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC); Hausdorff Distance (HD);

Scar quantification: Generalized Dice Similarity Coefficient (G-DSC); Accuracy (ACC); Sensitivity (SEN)

For LA multi-structure segmentation from CT (LAMS-CT):

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC); Hausdorff Distance (HD).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

For segmentation:

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) : DSC is well-suited for assessing the overlap or agreement between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth, making it particularly useful when the regions of interest in medical images may partially overlap.

Hausdorff Distance (HD) : Both DSC and HD provide quantitative measures of segmentation accuracy, allowing for objective evaluation of segmentation algorithms. DSC quantifies the degree of overlap, while HD measures the maximum distance between two sets, indicating the degree of boundary mismatch.

For scar quantification:

The segmentation results were first projected onto the segmented LA surface. Then, the Accuracy and Sensitivity measurement of the two areas in the projected surface, and generalized Dice score were used as indicators of the accuracy of scar quantification. The generalized Dice score is a weighted Dice score by evaluating the segmentation of all labels.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

In general, submitted algorithms are ranked by following steps:

1. **Metric-wise Aggregation:** Average each metric across all cases to summarize performance per metric for each method. Generally, we give all cases equal weights. This is because the challenge aims to emphasize both generalizability and accuracy.
2. **Normalization of Metrics:** Standardize metrics with different scales through rank-based normalization or similar methods to enable fair comparisons.
3. **Combining Metrics into a Composite Score:** Combine normalized metrics into a single score using weighted averages or similar methods. Here, we compute the sum of metric ranks as the final composite score.
4. **Ranking Methods:** Rank methods based on their composite scores, reflecting overall performance. Here, the team that has lowest composite score will get the best performance award, and ties are permitted when teams achieve identical scores.

Specifically, CARE-Left Atrium task will give 2 best performance awards, one for the LASQ-MRI subtask and one for the LAMS-CT subtask. We will provide multiple leaderboards, representing stratified performance across different test centers and substructures.

For the LASQ-MRI subtask, we will report DSC and HD of LA cavity and G-DSC, ACC and SEN of scar in leaderboards. However, we only use G-DSC, ACC and SEN of scar to rank scar quantification in this subtask. Specifically, we first compute the average value of these metrics across all cases. For each team, we then determine its rank for every metric based on these averages. Finally, the team's composite score is obtained by summing its ranks across all metrics.

Similarly, for the LAMS-CT subtask, we will report DSC and HD of 3 LA substructures (LA, LAA, PVs) in leaderboards. In the final ranking, we first compute the average value of each metric across all cases. Then we give LA, LAA, PVs all 33% weights to compute the weighted DSC and HD. For each team, we then determine its rank for every metric based on these averages. Finally, the team's composite score is obtained by summing its ranks across all metrics.

The team that has lowest composite score will get the best performance award in that subtask, and ties are permitted when teams achieve identical scores.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Only complete submissions are evaluated.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Metric-wise Aggregation: Each metric, such as Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Hausdorff Distance (HD), or other metrics, is averaged across all test cases to produce a single representative value for that metric and method. This step provides an overall summary of performance per metric. Here, we give all cases (in-domain and out-of-domain) equal weights, since the challenge aims to emphasize both generalizability and accuracy.

Normalization of Metrics: When metrics have different scales, normalization is applied to standardize the values. We adopt rank-based normalization for metrics. This step ensures comparability when combining multiple metrics into a single score.

Combining Metrics into a Composite Score: A composite score is calculated by combining the normalized metric values using a weighted average or another aggregation approach, The weights assigned to each metric can be

adjusted based on the evaluation criteria or the importance of each metric.

Ranking Methods: Methods are ranked based on their composite scores, with higher or lower scores indicating better performance depending on the optimization direction of each metric.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The mean and standard deviation, as well as all percentiles if needed, will be calculated for each group of results. Moreover, T-test will be used to determine if there is a significant difference between results of two participants, which would be helpful to analyze the final ranking results.

Specifically, nonparametric test such as Mann-Whitney U Test, KS test, or Bayes Factor will be utilized to determine the significance of top performing methods for small data.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

We assess precision by reporting the mean \pm standard deviation of performance metrics across the test set. To quantify estimation uncertainty, we also compute confidence intervals via bootstrapping.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD across test cases.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Nonparametric test such as Mann-Whitney U Test, KS test, or Bayes Factor will be utilized to determine the significance of top performing methods for small data.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

T-test will be used to determine if there is a significant difference between results of two participants, which would be helpful to analyze the final ranking results.

Note that we will perform case-wise paired comparisons for all method pairs $(N(N-1)/2)$ for each primary metric/structure. We will still highlight the top-k methods in the narrative, but the full pairwise results will be provided for transparency.

Moreover, Benjamini-Hochberg method or other similar methods will be used to control the false discovery rate in multiple comparisons.

Tests will be case-wise paired, since all methods are evaluated on the same set of cases.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Only teams that provide complete results are ranked.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

We mainly use python to conduct results analysis.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

None.

TASK 2: CARE-Liver: Liver Fibrosis Quantification and Analysis

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Liver fibrosis, often resulting from chronic viral or metabolic liver diseases, poses a significant global health challenge. Accurate liver segmentation (LiSeg) and fibrosis staging (LiFS) are crucial for assessing disease severity and enabling precise diagnoses. Managing chronic liver diseases such as cirrhosis and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD).

This task focuses on developing automated methods for liver segmentation and fibrosis staging using multi-phase, multi-center liver MRI scans. Automatic LiFS presents challenges such as missing modalities for certain patients, misalignments in multi-phase MRI data, and the need for effective integration of multi-phase information to improve the accuracy and generalizability of liver fibrosis diagnoses. Similarly, automatic LiSeg faces difficulties stemming from limited ground truth annotations across different modalities and domain shifts in multi-center datasets.

To address these challenges, the extensive use of external data and pre-trained models is encouraged to enhance liver segmentation performance. This track aims to foster innovative solutions that overcome these obstacles, leveraging multi-phase MRI data to advance the field of liver segmentation and fibrosis staging. Therefore, it can improve the diagnosis and treatment planning for various types of chronic liver diseases.

Building on the dataset used in CARE 2025, we have expanded the collection to include 190 newly acquired cases, bringing the total to 800 cases. These cases were obtained from the same vendors and centers, including Philips Ingenia 3.0T, Siemens Skyra 3.0T, and Siemens Aera 1.5T. The dataset features multi-phase imaging modalities such as T2-weighted imaging, diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI), and Gadolinium ethoxybenzyl diethylenetriamine pentaacetic acid (Gd-EOB-DTPA)-enhanced dynamic MRIs. The Gd-EOB-DTPA-enhanced dynamic MRIs include multiple phases: non-contrast, arterial, venous, delayed, and hepatobiliary phases.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Liver Fibrosis, Classification, Segmentation, Multi-Sequence, Missing Data, Misaligned data, Generalizability

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Xiahai Zhuang, School of Data Science, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Yuanye Liu, School of Data Science, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Yuxin Shi, Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Nannan Shi, Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Arif Mahmood, Department of Computer Science, Information Technology University, Lahore, Pakistan.

Murtaza Taj, Department of Computer Science, Lahore University of Management Sciences, Lahore, Pakistan.

Byung-Woo Hong, Department of Artificial Intelligence, Chung-Ang University, Seoul, Korea.

Hyun-Tae Choi, Department of Artificial Intelligence, Chung-Ang University, Seoul, Korea.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Xiahai Zhuang: zxh@fudan.edu.cn

Yuanye Liu: yuanyeliu@fudan.edu.cn

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes.

Nannan Shi: Dataset curation, and clinical advisor during validation.

Yuxin Shi: Dataset curation and annotation.

Fei Shan: Dataset curation.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

N/A

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

No

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

https://www.zmic.org.cn/care_2026/

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples).

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants may also include publicly available data, including (open) pre-trained nets.

Such additional data needs to be publicly available before the date of the test results submission.

Private annotations of such data is prohibited.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge has one best paper and two runner-ups. In addition, each (sub)task has one best performance award.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

We will release the leaderboard to announce performance results of all methods publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Every member in the participating teams qualifies as author.

The participating teams may publish their own results separately, and are required to cite our challenge.

There is an embargo time.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

We established an online evaluation platform and plan to use Docker for the testing phase. During the training and validation phases, participants can register on our platform and directly upload their predictions on the validation set.

To ensure a fair comparison, we adopt Docker for the testing phase, requiring participants to submit their Docker models for testing. The memory limit is pre-defined to 20GB. If any problem occurs in testing, we will contact participants through email and report corresponding error reason.

Please see the challenge website (https://www.zmic.org.cn/care_2026/) for submission guidance. An example of a container will be provided on the challenge website, with the input/output information for each task displayed in that example.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participating teams are allowed to evaluate their algorithms multiple times prior to final submission. Each team is permitted up to 10 submissions on the validation set for method development and tuning.

For the test phase, each team is allowed 2 submissions, and only the final submission will be considered for the official challenge results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration period: April 1st, 2026 - July 20th, 2026

Training data release: April 10st, 2026

Validation data release: May 1st, 2026

Test data release: June 20th, 2026

Test results submission: July 20th, 2026

Submission of abstract: July 30th, 2026

Submission of challenge paper: July 30th, 2026

Release date of final results: August 13th, 2026

Notification of challenge paper acceptance: August 13th, 2026

Challenge paper camera ready: August 27th, 2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

No ethics approval is needed.

The study had been approved by the institutional review board and the data had been anonymized.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The source code of evaluation won't be available. However, we will provide an online evaluation platform for long-term research purposes. We will ensure the online evaluation platform running smoothly, and prepare backup plans for emergencies. The metrics we adopted are commonly used in community and easy to reproduce the results. In addition, we will update a transparent specification for evaluation on the challenge website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants are encouraged to publish their code.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The sponsors are not decided yet.

Only organizers can have access to the test data labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Prognosis,CAD,Decision support,Treatment planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation,Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final

biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients with a wide range of Liver Diseased with multi-sequence MRI scans.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is same as the target cohort.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Multiple Sequence MRIs, including T2, T1, DWI and Enhanced MRIs.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional information.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Abdomen MRI scans

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Liver fibrosis staging: 4 types of fibrosis severity.

Liver segmentation: Liver structure.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness,generalizability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Philips Ingenia3.0T, Siemens Skyra 3.0T, Siemens Aera 1.5T

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Images in this task were collected from 4 centers, namely 2.A/B1/B2/C.

The image acquisition protocol is as follows:

For all images: FOV=280-380mm, Flip angle=9-10, matrix=180-320, slice thickness=2-3mm.

Dataset 2.A: Images were acquired using Siemens Skyra 3.0T, with TR/TE=1.3-1.5/3.4-3.8ms.

Dataset 2.B1/2.B2: Images were acquired using Philips Ingenia3.0T, with TR/TE=3.2-3.4/0 and 3.4-3.6/0ms, respectively.

Dataset 2.C: Images were acquired using Siemens Aera 1.5T, with TR/TE=3.8-4.0/1.2-1.4ms.

The dataset include multi-phase and multi-center data, consisting of T2-weighted imaging, diffusion-weighted imaging, and Gadolinium ethoxybenzyl diethylenetriamine pentaacetic acid (Gd-EOB-DTPA)-enhanced dynamic MRIs. Gd-EOB-DTPA-enhanced dynamic MRIs include the non-contrast phase (T1WI), arterial phase, venous phase, delay phase, and hepatobiliary phase. Contrast-enhanced scans were performed based on the injection of the Gd-EOB-DTPA agent. The arterial phase is captured 25 seconds after the contrast agent is injected. Subsequently, the portal phase is achieved 1 minute later. After another 3 minutes, the delay phase is obtained, and finally, the hepatobiliary phase is reached 20 minutes thereafter.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The data for this task was collected from 4 centers listed above.

In consideration of patient and institutional privacy and confidentiality, along with the study purpose of model generalizability, detailed information regarding the source of specific sub-datasets for each task will not be disclosed.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Experienced physicists specialized in liver MRI.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to MRI(s), with golden standard liver structure, and staging ground truth.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

This task has 800 cases in total.

Training set: 520 cases {2.A=170, 2.B1=250, 2.B2=100}

Validation set: 90 cases {2.A=30, 2.B1=30, 2.B2=30}

Test set: 190 cases {2.A=40, 2.B1=40, 2.B2=40, 2.C=70}

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

For Liver Fibrosis staging, all cases are annotated.

For Liver Segmentation, only 10% of training set is annotated, all of test set is annotated. Note that we annotated equal number of cases from each center to maintain variability of the annotated cases.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Considering the generalization of unseen centers, it is necessary to add centers that have not been seen in the training and validation sets in the test set. For the seen centers in the liver segmentation task, participants are encouraged to make better use of the unlabeled data, foundation model, and external datasets, thus providing few training samples with segmentation ground truth and large-range training data without segmentation ground truth.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

None.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Yes. We have added 190 cases for this task. The proportion of new data is $190/800 = 23.75\%$.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Each data had been manually delineated by doctor or well-trained observers who were not aware of the methodology of this work.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For the segmentation label, the annotators were instructed to segment the ROIs slice-by-slice, using the brush tool in the ITK-SNAP.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each task was conducted by different radiologists specialized in this field. For each task, PhD students first independently finished the annotation for each case and the average annotation was then checked and amended by a senior radiologist.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The final gold standard segmentation was achieved by averaging several manual delineations using the shape-based average approach if necessary.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

None.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Inter- and intra-annotator variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

For liver fibrosis staging (classification): Area under curve (AUC); Accuracy (ACC).

For liver segmentation: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC); Hausdorff Distance (HD).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

For liver segmentation:

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) : DSC is well-suited for assessing the overlap or agreement between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth, making it particularly useful when the regions of interest in medical images may partially overlap.

Hausdorff Distance (HD) : Both DSC and HD provide quantitative measures of segmentation accuracy, allowing for objective evaluation of segmentation algorithms. DSC quantifies the degree of overlap, while HD measures the maximum distance between two sets, indicating the degree of boundary mismatch.

For fibrosis staging:

Area under curve (AUC): It assesses the model's ability to distinguish between positive and negative instances across various threshold values.

Accuracy (ACC): It is a straightforward metric that measures the proportion of correctly classified instances out of the total.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

In general, submitted algorithms are ranked by following steps:

1. Metric-wise Aggregation: Average each metric across all cases to summarize performance per metric for each method. Generally, we give all cases equal weights. This is because the challenge aims to emphasize both generalizability and accuracy.
2. Normalization of Metrics: Standardize metrics with different scales through rank-based normalization or similar methods to enable fair comparisons.
3. Combining Metrics into a Composite Score: Combine normalized metrics into a single score using weighted averages or similar methods. Here, we compute the sum of metric ranks as the final composite score.
4. Ranking Methods: Rank methods based on their composite scores, reflecting overall performance. Here, the team that has lowest composite score will get the best performance award, and ties are permitted when teams achieve identical scores.

Specifically, CARE-Liver task will give 2 best performance awards, one for the LiFS subtask and one for the LiSeg subtask. We will provide multiple leaderboards, reporting stratified performance according to whether image is contrast-enhanced, and different test centers.

For the LiFS subtask, ACC and AUC will be reported in leaderboards. In the final ranking, we first compute the average ACC and AUC across all test cases for each team. For each team, we then determine its ACC rank and AUC rank based on these averages. The final composite score for a team is the sum of its ACC rank and its AUC rank. For the LiSeg subtask, similarly, DSC and HD will be reported in leaderboards. In final ranking, the average DSC and average HD are computed across all cases, and the composite score for one team is computed as the sum of team's ranks in the DSC and HD rankings.

The team that has lowest composite score will get the best performance award in that subtask, and ties are permitted when teams achieve identical scores.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Only complete submissions are evaluated.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Metric-wise Aggregation: Each metric, such as Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Hausdorff Distance (HD), or other metrics, is averaged across all test cases to produce a single representative value for that metric and method. This step provides an overall summary of performance per metric. Here, we give all cases (in-domain and out-of-domain) equal weights, since the challenge aims to emphasize both generalizability and accuracy.

Normalization of Metrics: When metrics have different scales, normalization is applied to standardize the values. We adopt rank-based normalization for metrics. This step ensures comparability when combining multiple metrics into a single score.

Combining Metrics into a Composite Score: A composite score is calculated by combining the normalized metric values using a weighted average or another aggregation approach. The weights assigned to each metric can be adjusted based on the evaluation criteria or the importance of each metric.

Ranking Methods: Methods are ranked based on their composite scores, with higher or lower scores indicating better performance depending on the optimization direction of each metric.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The mean and standard deviation, as well as all percentiles if needed, will be calculated for each group of results. Moreover, T-test will be used to determine if there is a significant difference between results of two participants, which would be helpful to analyze the final ranking results.

Specifically, nonparametric test such as Mann-Whitney U Test, KS test, or Bayes Factor will be utilized to determine the significance of top performing methods for small data.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

We assess precision by reporting the mean \pm standard deviation of performance metrics across the test set. To quantify estimation uncertainty, we also compute confidence intervals via bootstrapping.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD across test cases.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Nonparametric test such as Mann-Whitney U Test, KS test, or Bayes Factor will be utilized to determine the significance of top performing methods for small data.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

T-test will be used to determine if there is a significant difference between results of two participants, which would be helpful to analyze the final ranking results.

Note that we will perform case-wise paired comparisons for all method pairs ($N(N-1)/2$) for each primary metric/structure. We will still highlight the top-k methods in the narrative, but the full pairwise results will be provided for transparency.

Moreover, Benjamini-Hochberg method or other similar methods will be used to control the false discovery rate in multiple comparisons.

Tests will be case-wise paired, since all methods are evaluated on the same set of cases.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Only teams that provide complete results are ranked.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

We mainly use python to conduct results analysis.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

None.

TASK 3: CARE-Myocardium: Myocardial Pathology Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Myocardial infarction (MI) is a leading cause of mortality and disability worldwide. Accurate assessment of myocardial viability is critical for the diagnosis and management of MI patients. This track focuses on myocardial pathology segmentation (MyoPS) using multi-sequence cardiac magnetic resonance (CMR) imaging. The primary objective is to classify myocardial regions into healthy myocardium, scar tissue, and edema based on multi-sequence CMR data from MI patients.

The challenge emphasizes addressing key real-world issues, including the integration of multi-continent datasets, handling missing sequences from certain centers, and mitigating misalignments in multi-sequence CMRs. This track seeks innovative solutions that tackle these challenges, leveraging diverse and complex multi-sequence CMR datasets to advance the accuracy and reliability of MyoPS. Therefore, it can improve the accurate diagnosis, treatment planning and prognostic efficacy assessment of MI.

Building on the CMR sequences from eight centers used in CARE 2025, we have added 200 newly collected cases from patients with chronic myocardial infarction-defined as myocardial infarction occurring six months or more after an acute event-sourced from the existing centers and an additional center. Moreover, compared with previous events, we have added one new sub-tasks, focusing on segmenting myocardial pathology regions on the Cine sequence. This expansion provides participants with an enriched resource for training and evaluating algorithms, fostering the development of more robust and generalizable methods.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Myocardial pathology segmentation, Missing Data, Multi-Sequence, Misaligned data, Generalizability

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Xiahai Zhuang, School of Data Science, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Wangbin Ding, School of Medical Imaging, Fujian Medical University, Fuzhou, China.

Jiangbei Zhang, School of Data Science, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Fei Shan, Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Jiaye Tao, Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Yingliang Ma, School of Computing Sciences, University of East Anglia, U.K.

Freddy Odille, CIC-IT 1433, INSERM, Université de Lorraine and CHRU Nancy, Nancy, France. IADI U1254, INSERM

and Université de Lorraine, Nancy, France.

Bailiang Chen, CIC-IT 1433, INSERM, Université de Lorraine and CHRU Nancy, Nancy, France. 1ADI U1254, INSERM and Université de Lorraine, Nancy, France.

Shan Yang, Department of Radiology, Zhongshan Hospital, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Madina Mansurova, Department of Artificial Intelligence & Big Data, al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Xiahai Zhuang: zxh@fudan.edu.cn

Wangbin Ding: dingwangbin@fjmu.edu.cn

Jiangbei Zhang: 25210980135@m.fudan.edu.cn

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes.

Fei Shan: Dataset curation.

Jiaye Tao: Dataset annotation.

Shan Yang : Dataset curation and annotation.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

N/A

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

No

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

https://www.zmic.org.cn/care_2026/

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples).

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants may also include publicly available data, including (open) pre-trained nets.

Such additional data needs to be publicly available before the date of the test results submission.

Private annotations of such data is prohibited.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May not participate

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge has one best paper and two runner-ups. In addition, each (sub)task has one best performance award.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

We will release the leaderboard to announce performance results of all methods publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Every member in the participating teams qualifies as author.

The participating teams may publish their own results separately, and are required to cite our challenge.

There is an embargo time.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

We established an online evaluation platform and plan to use Docker for the testing phase. During the training and validation phases, participants can register on our platform and directly upload their predictions on the validation set.

To ensure a fair comparison, we adopt Docker for the testing phase, requiring participants to submit their Docker models for testing. The memory limit is pre-defined to 20GB. If any problem occurs in testing, we will contact participants through email and report corresponding error reason.

Please see the challenge website (https://www.zmic.org.cn/care_2026/) for submission guidance. An example of a container will be provided on the challenge website, with the input/output information for each task displayed in that example.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Maximum number of model evaluations on the validation set: 10 in total after the submission platform opens.

Maximum number of final model evaluations on the test set: 1 in total.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration period: April 1st, 2026 - July 20th, 2026

Training data release: April 10st, 2026

Validation data release: May 1st, 2026

Test data release: June 20th, 2026

Test results submission: July 20th, 2026

Submission of abstract: July 30th, 2026

Submission of challenge paper: July 30th, 2026

Release date of final results: August 13th, 2026

Notification of challenge paper acceptance: August 13th, 2026

Challenge paper camera ready: August 27th, 2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

No ethics approval is needed.

The study had been approved by the institutional review board and the data had been anonymized.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The source code of evaluation won't be available. However, we will provide an online evaluation platform for long-term research purposes. We will ensure the online evaluation platform running smoothly, and prepare backup plans for emergencies. The metrics we adopted are commonly used in community and easy to reproduce the results. In addition, we will update a transparent specification for evaluation on the challenge website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants are encouraged to publish their code.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The sponsors are not decided yet.

Only organizers can have access to the test data labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD, Treatment planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics

defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Acute/chronic myocardial infarction patients who underwent single/multi-sequence cardiac MRI scans.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is same as the target cohort.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Multiple Sequence MRIs, including LGE, T2, and cine MRIs.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional information.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

LV region shown in different MRI sequences.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Scars and edema of Myo.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness,generalizability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Philips Achieva 1.5T, Siemens Avanto 1.5T, Siemens Aera 1.5T, Philips Ingenia 1.5T.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Images in this task were collected from 9 centers, namely 3.A/B/C/D/E/F/G/H/I.

Dataset 3.A: Images were acquired with Siemens, General Electric, and Philips. The in-plane resolution of LGE scan was $(0.78-1.76) \times (0.78-1.76)$ mm, and the slice thickness was 2.5-20 mm.

Dataset 3.B: Images were acquired with Philips Achieva 1.5T. The in-plane resolution of LGE scan was $(0.70-1.36) \times (0.70-1.36)$ mm, and the slice thickness was 8-10 mm. The in-plane resolution of cine scan was $(1.19-1.45) \times (1.19-1.45)$ mm, and the slice thickness was 8-10 mm.

Dataset 3.C: Images were acquired with Philips Achieva 1.5T. The in-plane resolution of LGE scan was $(0.63-1.37) \times (0.63-1.37)$ mm, and the slice thickness was 8-10 mm. The in-plane resolution of cine scan was $(1.32-1.45) \times (1.32-1.45)$ mm, and the slice thickness was 10 mm.

Dataset 3.D: Images were acquired with Siemens Avanto 1.5T. The in-plane resolution of LGE scan was $(1.41-1.72) \times (1.41-1.72)$ mm, and the slice thickness was 8 mm. The in-plane resolution of cine scan was $(1.77-2.08) \times (1.77-2.08)$ mm, and the slice thickness was 8-9 mm.

Dataset 3.E: Images were acquired with Philips Achieva 1.5T. The in-plane resolution of LGE scan was 0.75×0.75 mm, and the slice thickness was 8 mm. The in-plane resolution of T2w scan was 1.35×1.35 mm, and the slice thickness was 12-20 mm. The in-plane resolution of cine scan was 1.25×1.25 mm, and the slice thickness was 8-13 mm.

Dataset 3.F: Images were acquired with Siemens Aera 1.5T. The in-plane resolution of LGE and T2w scan was 1.33×1.33 mm, and the slice thickness was 10 mm. The in-plane resolution of cine scan was 1.77×1.77 mm, and the slice thickness was 10 mm.

Dataset 3.G: Images were acquired with Philips Ingenia 1.5T. The in-plane resolution of LGE and T2w scan was 1.33×1.33 mm, and the slice thickness was 10 mm. The in-plane resolution of cine scan was 1.77×1.77 mm, and the slice thickness was 10 mm.

Dataset 3.H: Images were acquired with Siemens Prisma 3.0T. The in-plane resolution of LGE scan was 1.36×1.36 mm, and the slice thickness was 10 mm.

Dataset 3.I: Images were acquired with Siemens and General Electric. The in-plane resolution of LGE scan was $(1.03-1.82) \times (1.07-1.82)$ mm, and the slice thickness was 1.6-20 mm.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The data for task 3 was collected from 9 centers listed above across two continents.

In consideration of patient and institutional privacy and confidentiality, along with the study purpose of model generalizability, detailed information regarding the source of specific sub-datasets for each task will not be disclosed.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Experienced physicists specialized in cardiac MRI.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to MRI(s) with structure and myocardial pathology annotations.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

This task has 500 cases in total.

Training set: 395 cases {Centers: 3.A=81,3.B=50, 3.C=70, 3.E=7, 3.F=9, 3.G=8, 3.H=35, 3.I=130}

Validation set: 35 cases {Centers: 3.D=35}

Testing set: 70 cases {Centers: 3.B=25, 3.C=20, 3.D=25}

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

Training set: 67%

Validation set: 100%

Test set: 64%

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

It's important to have sufficient training data to train models effectively, especially for a challenging task like myocardial pathology segmentation. The choice of the proportion of training and test data is crucial for ensuring reasonable performance and accurate evaluation of the developed algorithms. Besides, one unseen dataset is reserved for testing, which could help assess how well the developed models can perform on previously unencountered images. This is an important aspect of evaluating the robustness and applicability of the algorithms in real-world scenarios.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

None.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Yes. In addition to the CMR sequences from 8 centers utilized in CARE 2025, we have incorporated 200 newly collected cases, from patients with Chronic myocardial infarction (Chronic myocardial infarction refers to amyocardial infarction that typically occurs six months after an acute myocardial infarction) at an additional center I. These images were acquired using Siemens and General Electric scanner, with an in-plane resolution of (1.03-1.82)x(1.07-1.82) mm and a slice thickness of 1.6-20 mm. The proportion of new data is 200/500 = 40.00%.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Each data had been manually delineated by doctor or well-trained observers who were not aware of the methodology of this work.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For the segmentation label, the annotators were instructed to segment the ROIs slice-by-slice, using the brush tool in the ITK-SNAP.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each task was conducted by different radiologists specialized in this field. For each task, PhD students first independently finished the annotation for each case and the average annotation was then checked and amended by a senior radiologist.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The final gold standard segmentation was achieved by averaging several manual delineations using the shape-based average approach if necessary.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

None.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Inter- and intra-annotator variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC); Hausdorff Distance (HD).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

For segmentation:

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) : DSC is well-suited for assessing the overlap or agreement between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth, making it particularly useful when the regions of interest in medical images may partially overlap.

Hausdorff Distance (HD) : Both DSC and HD provide quantitative measures of segmentation accuracy, allowing for objective evaluation of segmentation algorithms. DSC quantifies the degree of overlap, while HD measures the maximum distance between two sets, indicating the degree of boundary mismatch.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

In general, submitted algorithms are ranked by following steps:

1. Metric-wise Aggregation: Average each metric across all cases to summarize performance per metric for each method. Generally, we give all cases equal weights. This is because the challenge aims to emphasize both generalizability and accuracy.
2. Normalization of Metrics: Standardize metrics with different scales through rank-based normalization or similar methods to enable fair comparisons.
3. Combining Metrics into a Composite Score: Combine normalized metrics into a single score using weighted averages or similar methods. Here, we compute the sum of metric ranks as the final composite score.
4. Ranking Methods: Rank methods based on their composite scores, reflecting overall performance. Here, the team that has lowest composite score will get the best performance award, and ties are permitted when teams achieve identical scores.

Specifically, CARE-Myocardium task will give 2 best performance awards, one for the MyoPS subtask and one for the CineMyoPS subtask. We provide multiple leaderboards for each subtask, reporting performance across different test centers and substructures.

For the MyoPS subtask, DSC and HD of scar and edema substructures will be reported in leaderboards. In final ranking, the average DSC and average HD of scar and edema are computed across all cases of test data for each team, respectively. Then we give both scar and edema 50% weights to compute the weighted DSC and HD. The final composite score is defined as the sum of a team's ranks in the DSC and HD rankings.

For the CineMyoPS subtask, similarly, DSC and HD of scar will be reported in leaderboards. In final ranking, the average DSC and average HD of scar are computed across all cases, and the composite score for one team is computed as the sum of team's ranks in the DSC and HD rankings.

The team that has lowest composite score will get the best performance award, and ties are permitted when teams achieve identical scores.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Only complete submissions are evaluated.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Metric-wise Aggregation: Each metric, such as Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Hausdorff Distance (HD), or other metrics, is averaged across all test cases to produce a single representative value for that metric and method. This step provides an overall summary of performance per metric. Here, we give all cases (in-domain and out-of-domain) equal weights, since the challenge aims to emphasize both generalizability and accuracy.

Normalization of Metrics: When metrics have different scales, normalization is applied to standardize the values. We adopt rank-based normalization for metrics. This step ensures comparability when combining multiple metrics into a single score.

Combining Metrics into a Composite Score: A composite score is calculated by combining the normalized metric values using a weighted average or another aggregation approach. The weights assigned to each metric can be adjusted based on the evaluation criteria or the importance of each metric.

Ranking Methods: Methods are ranked based on their composite scores, with higher or lower scores indicating better performance depending on the optimization direction of each metric.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The mean and standard deviation, as well as all percentiles if needed, will be calculated for each group of results. Moreover, T-test will be used to determine if there is a significant difference between results of two participants, which would be helpful to analyze the final ranking results.

Specifically, nonparametric test such as Mann-Whitney U Test, KS test, or Bayes Factor will be utilized to determine the significance of top performing methods for small data.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

We assess precision by reporting the mean \pm standard deviation of performance metrics across the test set. To quantify estimation uncertainty, we also compute confidence intervals via bootstrapping.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD across test cases.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Nonparametric test such as Mann-Whitney U Test, KS test, or Bayes Factor will be utilized to determine the significance of top performing methods for small data.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

T-test will be used to determine if there is a significant difference between results of two participants, which would be helpful to analyze the final ranking results.

Note that we will perform case-wise paired comparisons for all method pairs ($N(N-1)/2$) for each primary metric/structure. We will still highlight the top-k methods in the narrative, but the full pairwise results will be provided for transparency.

Moreover, Benjamini-Hochberg method or other similar methods will be used to control the false discovery rate in multiple comparisons.

Tests will be case-wise paired, since all methods are evaluated on the same set of cases.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Only teams that provide complete results are ranked.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

We mainly use python to conduct results analysis.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

None.

TASK 4: CARE-Whole Heart: Whole Heart Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), recognized by the WHO as the leading cause of death globally, demand precise morphological and pathological assessments through the segmentation of key cardiac structures from medical images.

CARE-Whole Heart aims to achieve whole heart segmentation (WHS), including the extraction of individual substructures such as the left ventricle (LV), right ventricle (RV), left atrium (LA), right atrium (RA), left ventricular myocardium (Myo), ascending aorta (AO), entire aorta, and pulmonary artery (PA). Through precise whole heart segmentation, functional indices, such as the ejection fraction and myocardial mass, can be directly calculated to support surgical guidance. Moreover, analysis of the whole heart has the potential of detecting subtle functional abnormalities. Therefore, it can assist early diagnosis of CVDs patients with normal systolic function of the ventricles but are suspected to have abnormal function in other regions.

However, automated WHS faces several challenges, including variability in heart shape throughout the cardiac cycle, clinical artifacts such as motion blur and poor contrast-to-noise ratios, as well as domain shifts across multi-center datasets and differing imaging modalities like CT and MRI.

To address these challenges, CARE-Whole Heart provides 246 cases collected from 8 centers, supporting in-distribution and out-of-distribution performance evaluation for methods. Moreover, the diversity and clinical relevance of the dataset offer a broader spectrum of anatomical and pathological variations.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Whole Heart Segmentation, Multi-Modality, Generalizability

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Xiahai Zhuang, School of Data Science, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Hangqi Zhou, School of Data Science, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Fei Shan, Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Qingchao Chen, National Institute of Health Data Science, Peking University, Beijing, China

Byung-Woo Hong, Department of Artificial Intelligence, Chung-Ang University, Seoul, Korea

Guang Yang, Bioengineering Department and Imperial-X, Imperial College London, London, U.K.

Yingliang Ma, School of Computing Sciences, University of East Anglia, U.K.

Jiaye Tao, Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

Arif Mahmood, Department of Computer Science, Information Technology University, Lahore, Pakistan.

Madina Mansurova, Department of Artificial Intelligence & Big Data, al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Xiahai Zhuang: zxh@fudan.edu.cn

Hangqi Zhou: hqzhou21@m.fudan.edu.cn

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes.

Fei Shan: Dataset curation.

Jiaye Tao: Dataset annotation.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

N/A

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

No

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

https://www.zmic.org.cn/care_2026/

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples).

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Participants may also include publicly available data, including (open) pre-trained nets.

Such additional data needs to be publicly available before the date of the test results submission.

Private annotations of such data is prohibited.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May not participate

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge has one best paper and two runner-ups. In addition, each (sub)task has one best performance award.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

We will release the leaderboard to announce performance results of all methods publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Every member in the participating teams qualifies as author.

The participating teams may publish their own results separately, and are required to cite our challenge.

There is an embargo time.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>

- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

We established an online evaluation platform and plan to use Docker for the testing phase. During the training and validation phases, participants can register on our platform and directly upload their predictions on the validation set.

To ensure a fair comparison, we adopt Docker for the testing phase, requiring participants to submit their Docker models for testing. The memory limit is pre-defined to 20GB. If any problem occurs in testing, we will contact participants through email and report corresponding error reason.

Please see the challenge website (https://www.zmic.org.cn/care_2026/) for submission guidance. An example of a container will be provided on the challenge website, with the input/output information for each task displayed in that example.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Maximum number of model evaluations on the validation set: 10 in total after the submission platform opens.

Maximum number of final model evaluations on the test set: 1 in total.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration period: April 1st, 2026 - July 20th, 2026

Training data release: April 10st, 2026

Validation data release: May 1st, 2026

Test data release: June 20th, 2026

Test results submission: July 20th, 2026

Submission of abstract: July 30th, 2026

Submission of challenge paper: July 30th, 2026

Release date of final results: August 13th, 2026

Notification of challenge paper acceptance: August 13th, 2026

Challenge paper camera ready: August 27th, 2026

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

No ethics approval is needed.

The study had been approved by the institutional review board and the data had been anonymized.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The source code of evaluation won't be available. However, we will provide an online evaluation platform for long-term research purposes. We will ensure the online evaluation platform running smoothly, and prepare backup plans for emergencies. The metrics we adopted are commonly used in community and easy to reproduce the results. In addition, we will update a transparent specification for evaluation on the challenge website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants are encouraged to publish their code.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The sponsors are not decided yet.

Only organizers can have access to the test data labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients with a wide range of cardiac diseases (myocardium infarction, atrial fibrillation, atrioventricular block, tricuspid regurgitation, aortic valve stenosis, Alagille syndrome, Williams syndrome, dilated cardiomyopathy, aortic coarctation, and Tetralogy of Fallot)

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort is same as the target cohort.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

CT and MRI.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional information.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No additional information.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The whole heart shown in CT or MRI data.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Seven substructures of the heart, including left ventricular blood cavity (LV), right ventricular blood cavity (RV), left atrial blood cavity (LA), right atrial blood cavity (RA), myocardium of the left ventricle (Myo), ascending aorta (AO), and pulmonary artery (PA).

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness,generalizability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Philips 64-slice CT scanner, SIEMENS SOMATOM Force CT scanner, GE Revolution_CT scanner, Philips Achieva 1.5T, Siemens Avanto 1.5T, Toshiba Aquilion ONE CT scanner.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Images in this task were collected from 8 centers, namely 4.A/B/C/D/E/F/G/H.

For Dataset 4.A, the cardiac CT/CTA data were obtained from 64-slice Philips CT scanners using a standard coronary CT angiography protocol. The in-plane resolution of the axial slices is 0.78×0.78 mm, and the average slice thickness is 1.60 mm.

For Dataset 4.B, the cardiac CT/CTA data were obtained from a dual-source SIEMENS SOMATOM Force CT scanner or a high-end, single-source GE CT scanner using standard coronary CT angiography protocols. The original resolution is not available.

For Dataset 4.C and Dataset 4.D, the cardiac MRI data were acquired with a 1.5T Philips scanner or Siemens Avanto 1.5T scanner. A navigator-gated 3D balanced steady state free precession (b-SSFP) sequence was used for free-breathing whole heart imaging. The data were acquired at a resolution various from $(1.6 \times 1.6 \times 2)$ to $(2 \times 2 \times 3.2)$ mm.

For Dataset 4.E, the cardiac MRI data were acquired with Philips Achieva 1.5T scanner. At this centre, a range of cardiac MRI sequences related to Steady-State Free Precession (SSFP) were employed for diverse imaging needs. Typical sequences include a free-breathing high-resolution 3D Turbo Field Echo with a resolution various from $(0.84 \times 0.84 \times 1.5)$ to $(0.89 \times 0.89 \times 2)$ mm, Balanced Turbo Field Echo with Breath-Hold with a resolution various from $(1.18 \times 1.18 \times 6)$ to $(1.21 \times 1.21 \times 6)$ mm.

For Dataset 4.F, the cardiac MRI data were acquired with Siemens Avanto 1.5T scanner. A navigator-gated 3D balanced steady state free precession (b-SSFP) sequence was used for free-breathing whole heart imaging. The data were acquired at a resolution various from $(0.76 \times 0.76 \times 1.5)$ to $(0.92 \times 0.92 \times 1.5)$ mm.

For Dataset 4.G, the cardiac CT/CTA data were obtained from a Siemens SOMATOM Force CT scanner using a dual-source coronary CT angiography adaptive sequence protocol. The in-plane resolutions of the axial slices are various from (0.30×0.30) to (0.48×0.48) mm, and the slice thickness is 0.5 mm.

For Dataset 4.H, the cardiac CT/CTA data were obtained from a TOSHIBA Aquilion ONE CT scanner using a standard coronary CT angiography protocol (Coronary CTA, 120 kV). The original in-plane resolutions of the axial slices are various from (0.41×0.41) to (0.59×0.59) mm, and the slice thickness is 0.5 mm.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data for this task was collected from 8 centers across 2 continents.

In consideration of patient and institutional privacy and confidentiality, along with the study purpose of model generalizability, detailed information regarding the source of specific sub-datasets for each task will not be disclosed.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Experienced physicists specialized in cardiac CT / MRI.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to a CT / MRI image with whole heart structure annotation.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The data for this task has 246 cases from 8 centers, namely 4.A/B/C/D/E/F/G/H.

Note that in consideration of patient and institutional privacy and confidentiality, particularly along with the study purpose of model generalizability, detailed information regarding the source of specific sub-datasets for each task will not be disclosed here.

Training set : 106 cases {Centers: 4.A = 20, 4.B = 20, 4.C&D; = 20, 4.E = 26, 4.G = 20}

Validation set: 50 cases {Centers: 4.A = 20, 4.B = 10, 4.C&D; = 20}

Test set: 90 cases {Centers: 4.A = 20, 4.B=14, 4.C&D; = 20, 4.F = 16, 4.H = 20}

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

Training set: 100%

Validation set: 100%

Test set: 78%

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

We adopt the proportion of training, validation and test cases in the previous edition (CARE-WHS in CARE 2025), with the modification that move 20 cases in the test set to the training set, and include 20 new cases for the test set.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

None.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Yes. In addition to data utilized in CARE 2025, we have incorporated 20 CTA scans for this task from a new center, referred to as center 4.H. The proportion of new data is $20/246 = 8.1\%$. These images were acquired using a TOSHIBA Aquilion ONE CT scanner using a standard coronary CT angiography protocol (Coronary CTA, 120 kV), and were resampled to $1 \times 1 \times 1$ mm.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Each data had been manually delineated by doctor or well-trained observers who were not aware of the methodology of this work.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For the segmentation label, the annotators were instructed to segment the ROIs slice-by-slice, using the brush tool in the ITK-SNAP.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each task was conducted by different radiologists specialized in this field. For each task, PhD students first independently finished the annotation for each case and the average annotation was then checked and amended by a senior radiologist.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The final gold standard segmentation was achieved by averaging several manual delineations using the shape-based average approach if necessary.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

None.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Inter- and intra-annotator variability.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC); Hausdorff Distance (HD).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

For segmentation:

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) : DSC is well-suited for assessing the overlap or agreement between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth, making it particularly useful when the regions of interest in medical images may partially overlap.

Hausdorff Distance (HD) : Both DSC and HD provide quantitative measures of segmentation accuracy, allowing for objective evaluation of segmentation algorithms. DSC quantifies the degree of overlap, while HD measures the maximum distance between two sets, indicating the degree of boundary mismatch.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

In general, submitted algorithms are ranked by following steps:

1. Metric-wise Aggregation: Average each metric across all cases to summarize performance per metric for each method. Generally, we give all cases equal weights. This is because the challenge aims to emphasize both generalizability and accuracy.
2. Normalization of Metrics: Standardize metrics with different scales through rank-based normalization or similar methods to enable fair comparisons.
3. Combining Metrics into a Composite Score: Combine normalized metrics into a single score using weighted averages or similar methods. Here, we compute the sum of metric ranks as the final composite score.
4. Ranking Methods: Rank methods based on their composite scores, reflecting overall performance. Here, the

team that has lowest composite score will get the best performance award, and ties are permitted when teams achieve identical scores.

Specifically, CARE-Whole Heart task will give 2 best performance awards according to performances across CT images and MRI images, respectively.

We will provide multiple leaderboards, representing stratified performance across different test centers and modalities. In each leaderboard, in addition to DSC and HD of 7 cardiac substructures, we will also report DSC and HD of whole heart segmentation (WHS), which are weighted average (according to their volumes) from 7 substructures.

We only use DSC and HD of WHS for final ranking. Specifically, we first compute the average Dice and average HD of WHS across all cases of test data. After that, the composite score for one team is computed as the sum of team's ranks in the DSC and HD rankings.

The team that has lowest composite score will get the best performance award, and ties are permitted when teams achieve identical scores.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Only complete submissions are evaluated.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Metric-wise Aggregation: Each metric, such as Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Hausdorff Distance (HD), or other metrics, is averaged across all test cases to produce a single representative value for that metric and method. This step provides an overall summary of performance per metric. Here, we give all cases (in-domain and out-of-domain) equal weights, since the challenge aims to emphasize both generalizability and accuracy.

Normalization of Metrics: When metrics have different scales, normalization is applied to standardize the values. We adopt rank-based normalization for metrics. This step ensures comparability when combining multiple metrics into a single score.

Combining Metrics into a Composite Score: A composite score is calculated by combining the normalized metric values using a weighted average or another aggregation approach, The weights assigned to each metric can be adjusted based on the evaluation criteria or the importance of each metric.

Ranking Methods: Methods are ranked based on their composite scores, with higher or lower scores indicating better performance depending on the optimization direction of each metric.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The mean and standard deviation, as well as all percentiles if needed, will be calculated for each group of results. Moreover, T-test will be used to determine if there is a significant difference between results of two participants, which would be helpful to analyze the final ranking results.

Specifically, nonparametric test such as Mann-Whitney U Test, KS test, or Bayes Factor will be utilized to

determine the significance of top performing methods for small data.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

We assess precision by reporting the mean \pm standard deviation of performance metrics across the test set. To quantify estimation uncertainty, we also compute confidence intervals via bootstrapping.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD across test cases.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Nonparametric test such as Mann-Whitney U Test, KS test, or Bayes Factor will be utilized to determine the significance of top performing methods for small data.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

T-test will be used to determine if there is a significant difference between results of two participants, which would be helpful to analyze the final ranking results.

Note that we will perform case-wise paired comparisons for all method pairs ($N(N-1)/2$) for each primary metric/structure. We will still highlight the top-k methods in the narrative, but the full pairwise results will be provided for transparency.

Moreover, Benjamini-Hochberg method or other similar methods will be used to control the false discovery rate in multiple comparisons.

Tests will be case-wise paired, since all methods are evaluated on the same set of cases.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

Only teams that provide complete results are ranked.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

We mainly use python to conduct results analysis.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

None.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

None.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

None.